

A Potentially Successful Market for the IKEA Group: Argentina

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ABSTRACT

Many International Economics textbooks report that companies investing abroad without any preliminary market analysis are a lot more than expected. In fact, all business organizations with an interest in internationalization should first take into consideration a range of variables, including geographical as well as cultural distance. It goes without saying that the shorter the distance, the lower the perceived risk. Because cultural traditions are reflected, among other things, in consumption models and consequently account for different types of promotion and distribution, knowing the culture of the country whose economy one is meant to enter will avoid unpleasant surprises at a later date. The goal of this essay is to gain a better understanding of the needs of young Argentines by using a sample of 1,000 individuals, aged between 18 and 30 years, who belonged to different social classes, fell into different consumer behavior groups, and predominantly lived in the Buenos Aires district – this age class amounts to 35% of the total population in Argentina, while inhabitants of the Buenos Aires district amount to 65% of the same total population. Accordingly, a survey was carried out and organized into different stages, with qualitative interviews and questions relating to their evaluation of products of foreign companies that are not present in the Argentine market, IKEA being one of these.

Keywords: local culture, country of origin effect, competitive advantage, internationalization, mktg mix;

1. Argentine Culture and Society

Argentine culture arose out of a blending of various peoples who have kept on emigrating to South-America throughout the centuries and from their not always peaceful relations with local populations. This essay is not supposed to deal with the history of this country but it is worth noting that today's Argentine culture is a combination of native European – mainly Spanish, Italian and Polish – and Arab traditions (L. Zanatta, 2010). This produced a profile that is similar from a cultural point of view to that of Mediterranean populations, with a core of strong family values, a sexist (male chauvinist) attitude, religious and fatalistic views. Argentines regard as fundamental to spend time with family and friends, and such need results in their habit to drink *maté* together. The practice of offering *maté* is the cultural equivalent of the Italian practice of offering *caffè* but is associated to a deeper social meaning.

Maté is a beverage made from dried *maté* leaves and boiling water – there is a summer type too, called *tereré*, though this is more common among tropical populations – and served with a metal straw from a small vessel. The vessel and the straw are shared by those who offer and those who

are offered the drink: so, in between sips of *maté*, people talk and stay together. One person only is meant to *cebar el mate*, that is to pour the boiling water into the vessel, while each of those present drinks up in turn and hands it to the *cebador* who refills it for the following guest. This is so important a social custom that when a teen-ager first feels the need to prepare a *maté* is said to be about to enter adult life.

Nowadays, Argentina's network of contacts with other populations and cultures is not so wide. Buenos Aires is the most cosmopolitan city in the country even though no steady flow of foreigners is recorded that could be compared to what occurs in other capital cities across the world. In addition to immigration from such closer countries as Uruguay, Paraguay and Bolivia, there are only some Brazilians, who have a preference for Argentina as their holiday destination, and Chileans. Setting tourists aside, the concentration of foreigners who are not from South America is definitely lower. US citizens generally move to Argentina for short periods – between one and three months – principally for tourism or to join voluntary associations. There are also online companies whose specific purpose is to provide internship placements and volunteer projects for foreigners who will thus join a group composed of

other foreigners: such experience does not enable them to gain any real insight into Argentina.

As regards Europeans, these usually go to Argentina either for their holidays or to visit relatives, this latter being often the case of Italians and Spanish. Descendants of immigrants develop a range of relationships with the culture of their origin:

- Those who fall into the first group of descendant are strongly bound to the native country of their great-grandparents, grandparents, or parents. They not seldom attend classes of their ancestors' language (e.g., Italian), usually speak a few words in the dialect of their native city or area, and are members of regional clubs that organize festivals, events and language courses.
- Descendants falling into the second group know little or nothing of their origins, because memory of them was lost as a consequence of their ancestors' psychological and economic distress.
- Descendants of the third type only have a vague idea of their roots and every now and then show an interest in the native country of their ancestors.

As regards social classification, the following categories can be found:

- **Low class:** it is composed of those who live in the so-called *villas*, generally receive economic help from the government, may have low-paying jobs, like cardboard boxes collection, or get into drug-dealing and stealing. They usually have large families so as to access more generous welfare benefits; theirs is a survival-oriented consumption;
- **Middle class:** those who belong to this class are generally employed in the public (e.g., school, police) or professional sector, and in buying personal and home products they are concerned about quality to price ratio. Those whose consumption has been restricted to food items, dress, and

everyday needs also fall into this group;

- **Upper class:** it is usually composed of doctors, entrepreneurs, etc, whose average family size is five members. They enjoy good or even high levels of disposable income and the richest among them can afford high quality and branded imported products. Those who are just well-off prefer goods of medium/high quality and what they purchase is the outcome of a selection.

Argentines speak a variety of Spanish called *castellano argentino*. This variety can be distinguished from that spoken in Spain on account of phonetic, lexical, morphological and syntactical differences. As a variety, it also shares a number of lexical features with Italian and particularly with certain dialects spoken in Southern Italian regions and in Genoa. A common joke among linguists has it that Italian is not spoken in Argentina in place of Spanish for the simple reason that Italians did not understand each other, as most immigrants' linguistic skills were limited to their own regional dialect.

Cities in Argentina were built recently and designed according to the typical US layout: there are blocks, called *cuadras* or *manzanas*, and while only a few streets have a name – though this is more common in Buenos Aires – most of them are numbered: for instance, you have *calle 10 entre 8 y 9*. Diagonal streets and parks are also common. What Argentines take to be the center of their cities is the main street with shops. There are more one-storey family houses than buildings, that can actually be found in the biggest cities only.

Argentina is not fully developed and there are several changes to be made. For instance, one can notice the shortage of garbage bins: there are only a few of them that are to be found mostly in the parks and hardly ever along the streets. In fact, throwing litter on the streets is not even considered impolite. One may also notice the poor public transport service: no strict timetable is provided and you can have two buses running together, one behind the other, and no bus is then to be seen for half an hour.

However, some slight improvements can also be seen such as the increasing number of CCTV cameras monitoring the streets at night, new and

faster bus routes, more bins in the streets. Time is obviously needed to achieve a better management and one should not forget that Argentina has just emerged from a severe crisis. Moreover, problems of this kind are also recorded in certain regions of more developed countries, Southern Italy being a case in point.

The public administration has become quite efficient thanks to a reform that dates back to four years ago and has been speeding up bureaucratic processes. Cases are dealt with quickly, also when applications are submitted by foreigners. For instance, visas are promptly issued by the immigration office.

The level of education is uniform across social stratifications whereas certain groups are emerging whose purchasing power is increasingly high. No convergence is recorded towards higher income per head yet, even though an increase is evident in certain social strata that will likely account for the diffusion of new types of product among these very strata. Major European companies may thus expand to Argentina since what they offer better meet these new needs of customers.

Levitt's theory on the globalization of markets (1983) – whereby the ongoing global standardization allows for an increasingly homogeneous market – is not fully consistent on account of the persistence of more or less deep and relevant cultural differences. These differences regard the socio-cultural contexts, frameworks and models; consumption behavior; industrial development patterns; political and law systems; infrastructures; production and distribution features; technological progress.

Despite its largely European origins, Argentine culture differs greatly from the cultures out of whose blending it arose. The presence of multinational companies and the steady flow of information favored by mass media are not enough to make Levitt's theory a necessary consequence of trends in Argentina too. Nevertheless, several tendencies can be observed, especially among the young people, that draw them closer to the young Europeans' standard consumption patterns.

On the whole, it can be finally argued that Argentina as a market is being explored with a certain tardiness and the economic analysis method that is most often adopted in these

explorations is a market evaluation based on analogy (Valdani & Bertoli, 2006).

2. Hofstede's Dimensions Applied to Argentina

In 1980, a Dutch social psychologist, Geert Hofstede, conducted a survey for an important multinational company on a sample of 116,000 people from 72 countries. This research enabled him to identify and accordingly assess four "dimensions of national culture" through which cultural analogies and differences among the countries under scrutiny could be evaluated.

The first dimension is *Power Distance* and refers to the degree of inequality among individuals that is recognized as "natural" and "adequate" by members of a certain culture. In Argentina this distance is assessed to be 49. Therefore, one would expect that the authority of those who are on a super-ordinate level of the social hierarchy is accepted by those on lower levels, but not so much as it occurs in other cultures that endorse higher distances: in Italy, for instance, this distance is 50. As a likely consequence, when it comes to marketing planning, companies should take into consideration that consumers are likely influenced by the opinions of the persons who are considered important.

The *Uncertainty Avoidance* index is 86 in Argentina, which is relatively high (it is 75 in Italy). This means that tolerance towards uncertainty is low and persons tend to control everything in such a way that unexpected turns are avoided: they do not accept rapid changes and are generally risk-averse. According to Hofstede, Catholic societies have a lower tolerance for ambiguity and are consequently ruled according to several laws and institutions so as to decrease the degree of uncertainty. It follows that, as far as companies operating in these societies are concerned, these have to follow strategies meant to position their products as safe.

Individualism in Argentina is assessed to be 46. Such figure refers to the extent to which people in a given country prefer to act as individuals rather than as members of a group. The degree of individualism in Argentina – the same degree is recorded in Japan, whereas it is 76 in Italy – ultimately reveals a collectivist society, where individuals are emotionally integrated into their

group, family or company. Individuals care about the interests of their group and hold as important the opinions and beliefs established within that group, that, in turn, offers them protection. Being accepted by a group – no matter whether of a social or economic character – is a really complex process that takes a long time, but then, once integrated, you can always rely on all the other members.

Masculinity is 56 in Argentina and this discloses that female presence is relatively developed in social and economic contexts. *Masculinity* is 70 in Italy and 95 in Japan.

A further index was proposed in 1988, *Confucian Dynamism* or *Long-term Orientation* (Hofstede & Bond, 1988). This index refers to the people's inclination to assume a long-term perspective and to their disposition to prioritize future benefits to the detriment of immediate advantages. This is not a typically Argentine attitude. Finally, as regards the *Dimension of Time* (Hall, 1977), like in most Mediterranean societies, hours in Argentina are perceived to be not so much definite temporal terms as broad indications.

3. Consumption Patterns

It can be argued that, on the whole, Argentines buy without any consumerist exaggeration and actually have an inclination to re-cycle objects. This attitude can be observed in middle and lower classes, while a proportion of people from the upper classes are increasingly assimilating consumer behaviors typical of Europeans, even though retaining a disposition to use again what they already own.

Before focusing on the Argentines' consumption, let us consider a well known index, the *Big Mac Index*, developed by a weekly news publication, *The Economist*. Essentially, this index measures the purchasing power in different countries by using the relative variations in the price of the Big Mac, the most famous of *McDonald's* burgers.

On average, in 2011 a Big Mac cost US\$ 4.84 in the Eurozone, US\$ 3.58 in the United States, and the equivalent of US\$ 3.82 in Argentina. This means that the purchasing power is quite high.

The following table was drawn by the National Institute of Statistics and Census (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, INDEC) and shows household consumption patterns in Argentine regions in 2008.

Finalidad del gasto	Total del país (%)	Región					
		Gran Buenos Aires	Pampeana	Noroeste	Noreste	Cuyo	Patagonia
		%					
Total Gasto de Consumo	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Alimentos y bebidas	33,4	31,3	34,0	40,5	39,1	33,6	30,4
Indumentaria y calzado	8,3	7,2	8,7	10,2	9,3	9,4	10,7
Propiedades, combustibles, agua y electricidad	10,8	10,6	11,1	9,2	11,6	11,1	12,1
Equipamiento y mantenimiento del hogar	7,2	7,3	7,1	6,8	8,3	7,0	7,2
Salud	7,6	8,4	7,9	6,0	4,8	7,3	4,8
Transporte y comunicaciones	15,2	16,1	14,5	12,7	13,6	15,4	17,3
Esparcimiento	8,2	9,0	8,1	6,2	6,1	6,8	9,2
Enseñanza	3,1	3,9	2,5	2,7	2,1	3,1	2,9
Bienes y servicios varios	6,1	6,3	6,1	5,8	5,2	6,2	5,4

The following table (source: INDEC 2008) shows the composition of families in each region and the percentages of households owning a car and with access to water and telephone services.

	Total del país (%)	Región					
		Gran Buenos Aires	Pampeana	Noroeste	Noreste	Cuyo	Patagonia
% sobre el total de hogares	100,00	33,96	37,69	10,21	6,68	6,63	4,83
Indicadores promedio							
Miembros por hogar	3,40	3,19	3,22	4,20	3,99	3,73	3,45
Menores de 14 años por hogar	0,90	0,75	0,80	1,33	1,41	1,05	0,98
Adultos de 65 años y más por hogar	0,35	0,37	0,37	0,30	0,24	0,34	0,22
Perceptores de ingreso en el hogar	1,81	1,83	1,77	1,95	1,71	1,91	1,75
Activos por hogar	1,60	1,64	1,51	1,78	1,56	1,72	1,52
Miembros por cuarto de uso exclusivo por hogar	1,30	1,18	1,24	1,65	1,52	1,41	1,29
Edad del Jefe del hogar	50	51	51	49	47	50	47
Adultos equivalentes por hogar	2,72	2,55	2,58	3,34	3,15	2,97	2,78
Porcentajes							
Hogares con Jefe activo	75,58	77,32	72,60	75,80	79,29	77,24	78,65
Hogares con Jefe asalariado	49,86	50,82	46,29	52,12	52,15	53,65	57,79
Hogares propietarios de la vivienda	67,46	67,41	68,35	68,35	65,74	60,30	71,14
Hogares inquilinos de la vivienda	15,94	16,01	17,62	9,81	10,19	20,40	17,05
Hogares sin agua corriente distribuida en la vivienda	10,17	6,57	6,62	25,41	30,05	8,74	5,53
Hogares con teléfono	75,13	86,17	77,81	45,98	52,71	70,17	75,96
Hogares que disponen de automóvil	31,75	32,32	35,31	17,72	18,55	38,32	38,82

Región	Gasto de consumo medio mensual por hogar	Gasto de consumo medio mensual per cápita
		\$
Total del País	1242,08	365,3
Gran Buenos Aires	1565,87	490,9
Ciudad de Buenos Aires	2113,45	812,9
Partidos del Gran Buenos Aires	1327,89	386,0
Pampeana	1168,41	362,9
Noroeste	868,83	206,9
Noreste ¹	805,78	201,9
Cuyo	1067,06	286,1
Patagonia	1170,72	339,3

Finalidad del gasto	Total del país (%)	Cantidad de miembros del hogar				
		Un miembro	Dos miembros	Tres miembros	Cuatro miembros	Cinco miembros y más
		%				
Total gasto de consumo	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Alimentos y bebidas	33,4	29,4	30,7	32,6	33,2	37,7
Indumentaria y calzado	8,3	8,0	7,1	8,4	8,4	9,2
Propiedades, combustibles, agua y electricidad	10,8	15,8	12,6	11,1	9,5	8,5
Equipamiento y mantenimiento del hogar	7,2	7,9	7,5	7,3	7,3	6,5
Salud	7,6	9,5	11,0	7,5	6,4	5,6
Transporte y comunicaciones	15,2	12,4	15,0	15,8	16,5	14,8
Esparcimiento	8,2	9,4	8,7	8,3	8,4	7,3
Enseñanza	3,1	1,8	1,6	2,8	4,2	4,1
Bienes y servicios varios	6,1	5,8	5,7	6,2	6,2	6,3

The tables above (data by INDEC 2008) show monthly total household expenditure, per capita expenditure, and consumption patterns according to household size.

The table below shows the consumption patterns in the Buenos Aires area, the one with the largest population among Argentine regions.

Finalidad del Gasto = Consumption patterns / Number of Household Members / One, Two, Three, Four, Five or more members /

Total consumer expenditure

Food and beverages

Clothes and footwear

Property, fuel, water and electricity

Home furniture and maintenance

Health

Transport and communication

Leisure time

Education

Other goods and services

Finalidad del gasto	Gran Buenos Aires	Lugar de residencia	
		Ciudad de Buenos Aires	Partidos del Gran Buenos Aires
		%	
Total gasto de consumo	100,0	100,0	100,0
Alimentos y bebidas	31,3	27,0	34,3
Indumentaria y calzado	7,2	7,1	7,3
Propiedades, combustibles, agua y electricidad	10,6	13,6	8,5
Equipamiento y mantenimiento del hogar	7,3	7,7	7,0
Salud	8,4	9,8	7,4
Transporte y comunicaciones	16,1	14,7	17,1
Esparcimiento	9,0	10,1	8,2
Enseñanza	3,9	4,0	3,9
Bienes y servicios varios	6,3	6,1	6,4

Finalidad del gasto = Consumption patterns / Buenos Aires Area / Place of Residence / Buenos Aires City / Buenos Aires Suburban Areas

Total consumer expenditure

Food and beverages

Clothes and footwear

Property, fuel, water and electricity

Home furniture and maintenance

Health

Transport and communication

Leisure time

Education

Other goods and services

The average Argentine consumer is concerned with the price of goods, avoids throwaway products, as s/he prefers non-disposable ones. Disposable glasses and plates are hardly ever used and therefore come in small packages only in most shops. Argentines prefer to call small stores rather than large supermarkets, as they find this to be a quicker and often cheaper way to shop. There is at least one or two stalls in each *cuadra* or block. More about commercial distribution is to be read below. Moreover, Argentines are not so inclined to change and remain faithful to products and shops.

Consumerism is not an issue in Argentina. The unnecessary does not appeal and items being bought almost always meet basic needs. From a commercial point of view, the Christmas season only starts during the week prior to Christmas day. Media do not broadcast or air advertisements of 'panettone' or of any other product typical of this festivity. Shops display Christmas packages later than in more developed countries.

What should be pointed out is that the previous ones are only general observations regarding consumption patterns. Obviously, different and new trends are also reported, especially among the young, and these will be dealt with in the following pages.

4. The IKEA case

After designing the general profiles through the already mentioned qualitative analysis, a range of companies were discussed and compared to the competition they are expected to find in Argentina. With respect to IKEA, its products and services were described and its marketing mix strategy presented. Interviewees were asked to point out the products they would have bought after reading through an IKEA catalog written in Spanish. Moreover, they were asked to state the maximum price they were ready to pay for a range of products. Results show that, as a general rule, inside prices are closer to those of the foreign companies examined, including IKEA, than to those currently paid for the products and services offered in Argentina.

4.1 Business Presentation, Organization and Mission

IKEA is a Swedish multi-national company established in the early twentieth century and currently based in the Netherlands. It is a furniture retailer and its mission is to provide customers with design products at competitive prices, while ensuring high quality and functionality, and showing respect for the environment. IKEA has supported charity foundations, like *Save the children*, and partnered with UNICEF: proceeds from the sales of SUNNAN solar-powered lamps have been donated to these very organizations. Besides, IKEA has committed to reducing emission of air pollutants – it has also partnered with WWF – and invested on renewable energy sources like wind, solar and others. In 2011 it provided approx. 150 shops with solar panels.

The IKEA group is controlled by *INGKA Holding B.V.*, a Dutch company that, in turn, is run by a Dutch not-for-profit organization: *Stitching INGKA Foundation*. *INGKA Holding B.V.* owns the industrial group, *Swedwood*, that provides the resources for the manufacturing of IKEA furniture and is also responsible for the design and development of the products. The logistics hub in Europe is located in Germany; the Asian logistics hub is located in Singapore. *Inter IKEA Systems B.V.*, in Holland, owns the IKEA concept, trademark and a network of franchises. The IKEA group is the largest franchisee of the *Inter IKEA Systems B.V.*, that is not owned by *INGKA Holding B.V.* It is the Luxembourgian *Inter IKEA Holding S.A.* – part of the *Inter IKEA Holding*, registered in Netherlands Antilles – that owns the *Inter IKEA Systems B.V.* The company owns all the lands and infrastructures it employs.

STRUCTURE OF THE IKEA GROUP OF COMPANIES

Source: *Welcome Inside*, IKEA group 2011 summary

In 2009, sales decreased by 1.1% worldwide because of the crisis. And yet, the company earned 4.4% more on account of the opening of new stores, a fall in the costs of raw materials, and a general reduction in expenditures. Total sales volume was 2.6 thousand million Euro, 2.1 of which were re-invested. IKEA is present in Europe, US, Oceania and Asia.

IKEA GROUP STORES WORLDWIDE

In 2010, the IKEA Group opened 12 new stores, in 7 countries.
On 31st August 2010, the IKEA Group had a total of 280 stores in 26 countries.

Source: *Welcome Inside*, IKEA group 2011 summary.

Percentages of sales in the different continents follow:

Source: *Welcome Inside*, IKEA group 2011 summary.

As for future openings, IKEA is interested in South Korea, India and Argentina.

4.2 Business Model

The company's *business model* allows for low prices and is based on a unique organization focusing on the following features:

- Development of new materials so as to save on resources;
- A narrow range of products manufactured by taking advantage of economies of scale and economies of learning. According to the company's balance sheets, prices have been decreasing by 2-3% every year for the last 10 years;
- Customers themselves assemble products and this accounts for a savings in terms of labor and transport. Products come in flat packages that can be stacked.

What follows is a practical example of IKEA business model. Several years ago, a market research conducted by IKEA pointed out a demand for small coffee tables designed to support small objects. The company's designers took inspiration from how doors are manufactured and created thin but resistant wooden honeycomb panels. The outcome was LACK, a lightweight, low-priced and easy-to-assemble coffee-table. It currently costs 4.90 Euro, in the face of a launch price of 8.99 Euro: such price has been falling thanks to the increase in sales that accounted for a reduction in production costs.

4.3 Market Potential Estimation

The goods manufactured by IKEA belong to the category of consumer durables. The following calculation can thus be used in order to estimate their market potential (Valdani & Bertoli, 2006):

$$\text{MktPot (market potential)} = (N * P) - U_{\text{uset}} + U_{\text{usestt}}$$

where:

- **N** refers to the number of potential customers, usually intended as either households or individuals;
- **P** is the percentage of subjects who can purchase a certain product without any significant impediment;
- **U_{uset}** refers to the number of units of a product already in use at a given time (*t*). This also amounts to the number of owners who must be excluded from the calculation of potential customers;

- **Usestt** refers to the number of units of a product that are not going to last much longer – on account of physical aging, psychological exhaustion, technical and economic obsolescence – and are going to be replaced soon.

To calculate the number of potential customers one should take the number of households – approx. 9 million according to the data supplied by INDEC in 2008 – and consider that no financial impediment is reported in 70% of them. Available data show that an average of 25 pieces of furniture are to be found in each household. Among the factors that most affect families' consumption is a desire to improve the appearance of their homes (Argentines are more likely to meet in their homes than in public places), the high number of weddings and therefore of young people leaving their native homes, and the fact that only a small amount of furniture was being sold for a good many years. However, the furniture industry is now recovering, also as a consequence of import restrictions and particularly of restrictions applying to wooden final goods. According to *Federación Argentina de la Industria Maderera y Afines-Faima*, the furniture industry increased by 25% in 2009. The main factories are to be found in Mendoza, Córdoba, Santa Fe and Buenos Aires. With respect to the commoner distribution channels, furniture and interior design goods are primarily sold in electronics and appliance stores or in small family shops.

$$\text{MktPot} = (225.000.000 * 70\%) - 161.105.504 + 60.414.564$$

Another means to measure a market potential is the market potential estimation by analogy, which includes a barometric analysis. The assumption behind it is that, should a direct relationship be established between the demand for a product and a certain indicator in a given country, then the existence of such relationship may be hypothesized in other countries too.

For instance, one should think of Southern Italy and of the similarities between the factors one may observe there and in Argentina. These factors are the lack of variety in the offer, social conditions, level of economic development, consumer patterns (such as a negligible inclination to consume and a preference for the products of

companies established in Italy and Europe), and the recent opening of malls.

These variables – which may be called YA, where A stands for the country under scrutiny, Italy in this case – affect the rise of XA demand. Accordingly, when YB factors – here B refers to Argentina – are tantamount to YA, they equally affect the rise of XB demand, here corresponding to the demand for IKEA products.

Since the very factors that accounted for the rise of the demand of IKEA products in Italy –lack of variety in the offer, the fascination exerted by products other than those commonly bought in local shops, and the enthusiastic reaction to (and visits of) the first malls – are also reported in Argentina, one may as well argue that they will account for the same increase in the level of demand in this latter country.

If one assumes that: $XA/YA = XB/YB$ with XA, YA and YB being known, it follows that: $XB = (XA)(YB)/YA$.

4.4 Value Chain: Primary and Secondary Activities

As far as inbound logistics is concerned, prior to the production process IKEA RAW MATERIALS buys part of the necessary raw materials from external suppliers while part of them are actually distributed by the operating holding company. As it comes to operations management, IKEA RAW MATERIALS sorts the materials and the projects among the outsourced suppliers where each article will be manufactured according to the relative project. The output of these manufacturers is controlled by IKEA agents who carefully check their production so as to explore new developments. These agents also negotiate prices, test the quality of products, and inspect the working environment in the factories. Most of the production of wooden furniture and home furnishing is carried out by SWEDWOOD, an IKEA industrial group with 32 factories in 9 countries, to which most of the wooden material is delivered. Finally, as regards outbound logistics, the industrial group SHEDWOOD and the other suppliers manufacture and send the end products

back to IKEA. This will in turn cope with their commercialization in the shortest possible time. From an economic viewpoint, the short distance between retailers, logistic centers, and suppliers is a most favorable feature. The distance between IKEA suppliers and consumers has been shortened and thus optimized from the point of view of transport costs and environmental impact. Marketing activities and sales are conducted through the internet and by means of advertising and catalogs. Additional services such as furniture

assembly and transport, and home delivery of the products purchased are also offered to the customers who ask for it.

As regards technology management, IKEA employs an online system that promptly answer the consumers' questions regarding hours, in-store availability, and information on how to reach the stores.

The IKEA value chain is characterized by distinguishing features that make it unique:

SOURCE: www.IKEA.com

The above model consists in a two-way value system between customers, suppliers and IKEA stores. According to such a global sourcing strategy, customers themselves turn into suppliers of time, labor, knowledge and transport. Accordingly, the company concentrates on customers whom it conceives of as value-consuming as well as value-generating. The management aims at building customers' loyalty, given that happy customers are loyal for longer, buy more, pay less attention to competing brands and provide the company with ideas on products and services. Reaching out to new customers is more expensive than building a loyal customer. IKEA's role in the value chain is therefore to stir suppliers and customers so that they will be enabled to provide useful information and to add value to the whole system. Besides providing the

company with valuable knowledge and opinion, customers deliver and assemble the products, thus generating a savings from which customers benefit and of which the company can take advantage.

In order to offer low-priced quality products to its customers, IKEA has to find suppliers that are able to meet such a demand. IKEA encourages long-term partnership agreements with its suppliers. Such a target also adds further value to the value chain of suppliers, who are thus enabled to develop economies of scale and of learning. The aim is to make the participants share the value that may be created by vertical integration, thus avoiding the organization costs that a supplying company would bear should it decide to absorb the supplying company to be found upwards on the productive chain. The insistence on low prices and sparing money is particularly effective insofar

as marketing is concerned: consumers who pay less for a product that they need are more likely to buy some other products.

4.5 Competitive Advantage

A fundamental principle for modern enterprises is the competitive advantage. This is enacted by the factors that can give companies an advantage in the competition to achieve, maintain or expand a market position. A company has a competitive advantage only when it is able to create a higher value than competing companies. According to Porter (Porter, 1985), a company can create a competitive advantage either by lowering prices in comparison to competitors or by differentiating its products in a way that enables them to charge higher prices than competitors. A cost-leadership strategy is mainly oriented towards the production and distribution of products rather than towards differentiation. A differentiation strategy entails major investments in plants and technological systems that are necessary to offer unique products to one's customers. A generic strategy of low-cost is effective only when the organization can charge lower prices for the same products or services offered by competing organizations. On the other hand, a differentiation strategy is implemented when an organization offers something unique, in that it can be distinguished from what is offered by competing organizations and its value is consequently perceived to be higher by the typical customer. When the differentiation is successful the company is allowed to charge a premium price, that is a higher price if compared to the average in the sector. Thus, certain as they are that the different quality is worth the higher price, customers are ready to pay it.

Whereas a cost-leadership strategy is mainly oriented towards the production, a strategy based on differentiation primarily focuses on the customer's requirements. According to the analysis of requirements, IKEA's target customers are young couples, single persons and working people who have little free time and limited economic resources. IKEA also targets the market of second homes and offices.

Even though selling to a wide range of potential customers, statistics showed that the IKEA typical

customer is a young family with low-middle income. As a consequence, the company's drive is to charge affordable prices for its products. The choice to charge low prices is meant to protect the group from competing organizations and replacement products. Moreover, it represents a major barrier to the establishment of new competing businesses. In order to develop a cost-leadership strategy and to gain a competitive advantage over the competition, companies may adopt a low-cost model that focuses on the operations management: the company selects suppliers that offer low-price products and employ low-cost logistics services including rail transport. To increase the use of long-distance rail transport is a forward-looking method of dealing with the fast moving consumer goods industry: not only has it positive effects on the environment, it also save time and money for the company. What is more, costs are further reduced for the company by leaving the furniture assembly and home delivery up to the customers. Other factors that add up to the competitive advantage of IKEA are: the focus and investment on innovation, the development of well-designed, simple and easy-to-assemble furniture that cannot be easily imitated by competing companies. The reduction of prices is also made possible by cutting additional services.

The company's purchasing strategy requires that large pieces of furniture, components, wardrobe doors, bed slats, utensils, and drawers are supplied by closer markets so as to ensure the steady and efficient supply of IKEA stores. As already mentioned, costs are also kept down by referring to the economies of scale and of learning developed by IKEA's clients thanks to the considerable volume of the very work orders placed by IKEA itself. Research activity and development planning are based in Sweden.

The group has a strong hold on its suppliers and a large portion of its production is fully outsourced. What accounts for its strong bargaining power is that the type of products and semi-finished products IKEA orders can be quite easily supplied by a number of competing factories. Accordingly, the group can always place orders with other factories should any of the current suppliers increase their prices. In this understanding, suppliers are forced to keep production costs down. Manufacturing suppliers and IKEA usually

sign long-term partnership agreements whose ultimate goal is to reduce production costs and to improve the quality of goods. As such, costs related to organization, specialized plant structures and workforce are avoided. Furthermore, both designers and suppliers are constantly looking for innovative materials; storage costs are reduced because the company directly owns the storehouses it uses; the uniformity of the shops all across the globe is preserved through a franchising model.

4.6 Internationalization of IKEA

IKEA has a range of foreign market entry modes: imports, exports, partnership agreements, investments. The global basis of its business model enables the exploitation of economies of scale while the ability to offer a standardized product encourages its expansion into new geographical areas. IKEA simultaneously passes through the four stages of the internationalization process: entry, establishment, development, and rationalization. Transfer pricing allows for the optimization of both positive and negative economic performances of the foreign societies owned by the group with respect to the tax regimes and while complying with the fiscal policies of the countries where these societies work.

IKEA has also made a significant contribution to the field of communication. This has been mainly due to a new notion of catalog, one which lists the whole range of products on sale and is structured according to an essentially promotional language and composition. The catalog reports the price of all products and the company is bound not to raise those prices throughout the year of the publication.

4.6.1 Strategy for Entering the Argentine Market

The most effective strategy IKEA may adopt in penetrating this new market is the implementation of Greenfield FDI. In fact, the company has already successfully implemented this strategy in the past upon entering other markets. Most firms developing a globally oriented strategy prefer a *greenfield* manufacturing site to an acquisition.

The reason is simple: efficiency is what companies of this kind want as they do not really have to adapt their products and strategies to local properties. Furthermore, their corporate identity is very strong and may thus clash with the local business and management culture in case of an acquisition. To implement Greenfield FDI anew in Argentina should prove to be a valid strategy on account of the demographic growth combined with the growth of economic factors and the high value of the Euro.

While to cover the whole of Argentina right from the beginning would be hardly possible, the investment should be made in the Buenos Aires area first and not in other regions because of the geographic dispersion that characterizes the national territory. The main harbors and airports are close to this area – by no chance called *porteña*, after the Spanish term for ‘harbor’, *puerto* – and the distribution is therefore better organized; plus, the majority of the population and most potential customers live here. The numerical development and the distribution across age classes not only reveal the current presence of a good many young people, but also points out that today’s children and young will become adults and set up house in the years to come.

A cost advantage could actually be realized by manufacturing directly in Argentina, particularly through the supply of raw materials, the handling of components and finished products, and the labor cost containment: the goods being considered are value-intensive and no skilled labor is required. A further advantage would be the elimination of custom taxes and transport costs. Moreover, the fact that the company manufactures in Argentina would ensure the opportunity to build up positive relationships with retailers, suppliers, and the local society in general.

Argentines attach great importance to reciprocity and would like to be involved in decision-making processes. In this understanding, to manufacture *in loco* would make sense, also because Argentine customers tend to buy products made in their own country more than foreign ones. This can be explained by the presumably higher reliability of local products but there are also clear historical reasons. Ever since Menem’s privatizations policies, when several local companies were taken over by foreign entrepreneurs who disregarded the

necessities of local communities, Argentines have come to prefer goods manufactured using national resources. Nevertheless, they are also willing to buy goods that, unlike national ones, may have their own major pluses, as is the case of the goods offered by IKEA’s business model. What is of the utmost importance is that the company be characterized by a positive country-of-origin effect and do not achieve a dominant position in already existing markets. Finally, one should also bear in mind that Argentina has maintained positive relationships of a commercial and political nature with Netherlands, so that the expected reciprocity could be taken for granted. The Argentine operational unit would therefore establish a global relationship with the holding company, with a certain degree of coordination, whereby the latter would be expected to introduce the new products and technologies for the whole group, while checking the activities undertaken on a local level. So, IKEA would meet the conditions described by Dunning’s Eclectic Paradigm. This paradigm comprises the three main trends observed in relation to FDI: economic theory of the industry, internationalization and localization. A company that aims to initiate an internationalization process has to meet the following three requirements:

- To own some sort of competitive advantage by virtue of its own business model, mission and general organization;
- To be able to fully exploit the opportunities created by such advantage by relying on one’s previous experience in different international markets;
- To be able to integrate all these advantages with factors to be found in the FDI destination country: cost advantages, supply of low-priced raw materials, lack of tough competition.

According to the present analysis, IKEA meets all of the above requirements. The degree of

coordination is high in that the new unit, like all the units in the other countries across the globe, will not have executive duties and will not be allowed to develop its own strategies or management policies. It goes without saying that the company will nonetheless be expected to start some kind of negotiation with Argentine identities so as to better adapt to local attitudes.

IKEA implements an undifferentiated global strategy: the widest possible range of activities are concentrated within one country and standardization is encouraged, while the activities down the value chain – those that must be carried out near the customers scattered across the global market – are closely coordinated.

Base products will therefore be standardized through the maximization of the economies of scale and of learning and by exploiting the comparative advantages offered by the host country. The strategy should be established according to a centralized development. Obviously enough, the full implementation of standardization is not possible and should actually coexist with, among other things, the differentiation of post-sale services.

The following table illustrates how the choice between local adaptation and global standardization – and their relative degree – should vary according to a set of strategic factors. As far as the positioning, name of the brand and focus on market segment are concerned, a full global standardization will be implemented: in this fashion, the company preserves its own distinguishing traits. The competitive strategy will be similar to that employed in most of the markets in which IKEA is present, as it hardly ever finds competing companies there that are able to provide the same products and services. Financial management and control can be partially adapted to local standards in consideration of the current trends in the exchange rate and the Argentine economic situation, so that they can be run in accordance with local attitudes and necessities.

Strategic Factor	Local Adaptation		Global Standardization	
	Full	Partial	Full	Partial
a. Strategic Orientation				

- Theme Positioning			x	
- Brand Name			x	
- Focus on Segment			x	
- Competitive Strategy				x
- Financial Management and Control		x		
b. Product/Service				
- Research and Development			x	
- Base Product			x	
- Product Design			x	
- Packaging			x	
c. Operations				
- Supply		x		
- Logistics		x		
- Production		x		
d. Marketing				
- Prices				x
- Advertising/Promotion		x		
- Channels		x		
- Sales Management		x		
- Assistance		x		

Source: Valdani, Bertoli, *Mercati internazionali e marketing*, Milano, EGEA, 2006, 88.

All concerning the product and relative services is fully standardized: this is the case of research and development, base product, product design and packaging. Supply, logistics and production activities are to some extent adapted to the Argentine context. The same applies to the marketing factor: IKEA retains its communication and promotion styles even though somehow adapting the content of advertisements to the market.

Internationalization will be productive and commercial, with a simple expansion strategy, while it will not affect the research and

development areas, since this will not be a learning market. A simple expansion regards the sale of the same products to market segment demands featuring similar characteristics to those in other countries. This strategy has to be complemented with a market development strategy, whereby foreign segments are partially different and it is therefore suggested that the same products be positioned in a slightly different manner. As a consequence, some products will be the same, while some others will be slightly different, more tuned to the local taste and more consistent with local desires. In planning, one

should take a proactive attitude rather than a reactive one, and such attitude should result in the following decisions: to assume a medium-long term vision, to gain a permanent position in the market, to try and introduce products that suit the local context, and to plan the company's communication. This attitude departs from a reactive one in that it is not based on the use of intermediaries during the internationalization process. The company's objectives are:

- to increase sales, even though this will not happen in the short term. To enter the Argentine market entails risks and costs that will only be recouped in the medium-long term;
- to meet preferably the demand of transnational segments with the same requirements reported in the markets already targeted. These segments are looking for the same benefits and are likely to react in a consistent manner to the company's marketing. This observation especially applies to consumers from high social classes whose behavior is close to the European one and, in fact, they want to enjoy the same benefits products or services that are enjoyed abroad;
- to diversify the risk. It is well known that the higher the number of markets in which one is present, the better chance one stands of diversifying so as to recoup losses due to possible failures.
- To benefit from the competitive advantages that can be afforded in the host country, and particularly from advantages relating to costs and supply services.

4.6.2 Advantages of Investment for the Market

The investment in Argentina would provide the following advantages for the new market and for the company itself:

- Creation of new jobs to build the necessary infrastructures, such as premises and car

parks, in the first place, and, subsequently, to run and manage the commercial structure;

- Predominant position in the market on account of the paucity and weakness of competition (this aspect will be further investigated below);
- The environment-friendly attitude of the company would appeal to those demand segments who are acutely aware of such issues as pollution and preservation of nature. In Argentina, this awareness is shared by several segments and corresponds to an incentive when buying a product, especially if buyers are young. Another aspect Argentine consumers would appreciate is the possibility to take the advice of the so-called 'planners' as to one's home furniture design: planners can be consulted through the IKEA website. Argentines like to rely on experts, regardless of their field and especially when it is free. And to be sure they do not love DIY.
- The possibility to find anything one may need to furnish their home in the one store; in Argentina problems are reported for those who do not own a car because of the inadequate transport service, especially across certain urban areas; this is a waste of time and dissuades one from moving, even though for a short distance only; the possibility to find a range of products in the same store allows for a reduction of such a waste of time; besides, the very variety offered by the company may result in an incentive.

4.6.3 A Comparison between the Prices Charged by IKEA and Argentine Competing Companies

First of all, this analysis takes into consideration ARREDO, a company that manufactures small home appliances and textiles similar to those sold by IKEA. In spite of this, the marketing mix strategies adopted by these two companies differ considerably. Subsequently, a comparison is drawn between the price charged by IKEA and the average price charged by its Argentine competition for the same items: this is represented

by such major furniture companies as FALABELLA, ROGELIO GONZÁLEZ and GIÚDICE.

A Comparison between IKEA and ARREDO Prices

ARREDO is an Argentine company specialized in home furniture and textiles. Its retail stores consist of small business premises to be found in most city centers; the design of its products slightly reminds of IKEA but their prices are not so competitive. In fact, ARREDO targets upper, middle-upper segments.

The following table compares ARREDO and IKEA prices for a list of products:

Product	ARREDO Price	IKEA Price
Sheets	Starting from 40 Euro	Starting from 7.99 Euro
Shower Curtain	Starting from 30 Euro	Starting from 10 Euro
Kitchen Textiles	Starting from 1 Euro	Starting from 2.99 Euro
Pillow Case	Starting from 5 Euro	Starting from 3.99 Euro

Prices charged by the ARREDO store in La Plata (Buenos Aires) in November 2010 and shown by IKEA's website at the same time (www.IKEA.com).

As already reported in a previous section, home furniture is usually sold in electronics and appliance stores; the most popular are ROGELIO GONZÁLEZ, FALABELAL and GIÚDICE. In the table below the prices charged by IKEA for certain exemplary products are compared to the average price charged by competing businesses:

ITEM	IKEA	LOCAL COMPETING BUSINESS (average)
Large Closet	Between 179 and 462 Euro	430 Euro
Bunk Bed	109 Euro	193 Euro
Mattress	Between 19.90 and 359 Euro	Between 65 and 482 Euro
Sofa	Minimum 89 Euro	311 Euro
Kitchen	Minimum 100 Euro	238 Euro

Prices could be read in the catalogs of Argentine companies and were shown on IKEA's website (www.IKEA.com), as of December 2010.

Mercado Libre is a website whose purpose and structure are very similar to Ebay's. It is used only in certain countries: Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Portugal, Ecuador, Costa Rica, Chile, Mexico, Panama, Peru, Dominican Republic, Uruguay and Venezuela. It is frequently used by Argentines who want to sell low-priced second-hand products and by upper middle class Argentines in particular: these are in fact aware of what is being sold in Europe and consequently want to trade imported products. IKEA articles are a case in point. Articles being traded can be either new or second-hand.

The table below shows a comparison between the price of IKEA articles sold through Mercado Libre website and their effective price:

Article	IKEA	Mercado Libre
Curtain	19.99 Euro	25.47 Euro, 29.24 Euro (new)
Closet	169 Euro	377.25 (second-hand)

2 Reading Lamps	4 Euro each	28.30 (second-hand)
6 Flowerpot Containers	1.99 Euro each	9.20 Euro (new)
Rug Blanket	3.99 Euro	16 Euro (new)
Pillows	3.99 Euro	41.50 Euro (new)
Magazine Rack	3.77 Euro	1.99 Euro (second-hand)

One can observe that most items are traded at a much higher price than that charged by IKEA. However, these items are still being sold and their demand is increasing.

4.6.4 Positioning and *Marketing Mix*

Segmentation

IKEA products are targeted at all types of consumers. However, in Argentina the company should focus on the middle and upper classes, because they not only have higher purchasing power but also attach great importance to the latest fashions and to the high social status associated with goods designed and sold by European brands. Those who belong to 'influential' social classes travel more, spend two hours online on a daily basis and thus interact with foreign consumer behaviors and cultures. They may thus be grouped into a 'transnational' segment who sometimes shares more with segments from other countries than with national ones.

Also the segment of young people between eighteen and thirty years of age is most appealing to IKEA, as already argued in the third section of this essay. Accordingly, IKEA should develop a continuum that ranges from standardization to adaptation to the contest, while keeping a consistent identity (once abroad the product and the relative communication are the same that can be found at home) and trying not to be regarded as too foreign, given that a risky *notinventedhere* syndrome is likely to be caused by such foreignness.

In Argentina, houses that are rented usually come either without any furniture or with some essential kitchen and drawer. Many tenants are young people, couples or single persons; houses are not so commonly shared by students and young workers as it occurs in Europe.

In conclusion, IKEA products are targeted at people who are ready to buy them primarily on account of what is reflected in its brand identity. Their aesthetical taste extends beyond the

furniture items they can find in local shops, and, since they are used to spend much of their leisure time at home, they wish to create a comfortable environment for themselves and their guests: hence they want to enjoy the benefits of low-cost home furniture design.

Product Policy

IKEA products offer the features of the "ideal product" pursued by several demand segments in Argentina: first, they have a favorable quality/price ratio; second, they communicate respect for the environment; third, they are regarded as an innovation in the field of home furniture; fourth, the company offers a wide range of products that are all available in the same store. IKEA products are perceived to be innovative and exert a 'prism effect', whereby the perception of the overall quality of the product is altered. In Argentina more than in other countries, this effect results in an amplification that makes the products appear to be of a higher level. They accordingly get a better positioning when compared to the local offer and are targeted at a higher class of people than in other countries. For instance, one should think of the United States where upper and middle class people consider IKEA products as low-budget products suitable to furnish the homes of students and low-income people.

The prism-effect to be noticed in Argentina is explained in the first place by the country-of-origin effect and the haloconstruct: such halo effect occurs when consumers do not have any experience of the country or of any product from there and still have formed a mental picture of that place based on their previous knowledge about it. The image of the country where a product is projected or designed or manufactured results in

beliefs about the properties of that product and a positive attitude towards its brand. However, this image may be only partially true or even fallacious. The perception one has of a nation is made of cognitive components – i.e., its political, cultural, economic and social typical characteristics – and emotional components – i.e., the feelings experienced toward that nation.

The dimensions of the image of IKEA's country are communicated through innovation, design, style, variety, elegance, balance of forms, prestige, exclusivity, high esteem, reliability, enduringness and quality. Being the country-of-origin effect a positive one, communication will have to remind of and strengthen the characteristics of the product as well as of the country of origin that are appreciated by the segment.

IKEA products will be standardized, as already argued, and standardization will follow a logic of production and marketing, but the introduction of products adapted to the new context is also possible. For instance, Argentine consumers demand products related to *mate* or *sommiers*.

Positioning is basically standard with regard to design, quality/price ratio, eco-friendly awareness, and the opportunity to find everything useful for home in the one store. On the other hand, adaptations regard the emphasis on the European origin of the project and its innovative character in Argentina. As a consequence, the company is positioned on the continuum that ranges from standardization to adaptation.

As for the definition of the product policy, it is necessary to take into consideration the following conditions:

- Conditions of the competition: in this case the competition is weak and the company's position in the market will be almost dominant;
- Market conduct: the taste of the demand is quite uniform;
- Conditions of the product: great importance to the economies of scale and opportunity to learn through the production of innovative products;
- Conditions of the company: IKEA's level of internationalization is high, as it is present in several, often big, markets. It

can count on a wealth of resources and adapt some products to the Argentine context without any major cost.

The standardization of the product allows for a scale-effect, a learning effect, and an increased market power. The larger the volume of standardized products, the more the raw material, semi-finished products and components purchased, and, as a consequence, the greater the market power in the relationship with suppliers. Moreover, adaptation costs are generally avoided, with a consequent saving that may allow for lower prices and greater competitiveness, and more investments in the promotion of the product. This could then be partially adopted to the new cultural context.

Spanish-language labels, directions for use, maintenance instructions and packages are already available and no adaptation is necessary in this respect too.

Finally, the IKEA Family Card should be promoted because Argentine consumers are used to loyalty cards of the stores where they shop and they like to think of themselves as privileged customers. The IKEA catalog also has to be promoted. Sales through catalog are appreciated because catalogs leave the impression of a direct contact with the retailer and those who usually take it easy and select the products carefully can thus take more time.

Communications Policy

This section deals with business communication. What should be borne in mind is that communications with institutions are essential in that they are expected to bring about an improvement in the relationships with the Argentine administrative system and a smarter penetration into the context being examined here. Argentine culture is of a low-context type. It is straightforward and a low degree of ambiguity characterizes the communicative level. And yet, it also presents some features typical of high-context cultures such as the importance of strong interpersonal relationships that one develops only after acceptance of the Other and a weak and not so independent law system. Also because of this system, one is lead to build interpersonal

relationships that may translate into psychological and emotional support within the social context.

When it comes to planning advertising campaigns the following questions have to be carefully pondered. The Argentine advertising style has to be analyzed and the mistake must be avoided of using again the Spanish-language advertisements that were previously run in Spain. Argentine language and culture differ substantially from their Spanish counterparts. Brands that assume the contrary may run the risk of being ostracized by Argentine consumers. Accordingly, verbal communication has to insist on the creation of messages whose goals are 1) to keep the corporate image intact and its spirit alive, and 2) to adapt such spirit to a type of irony that may be culturally acceptable. As far as non-verbal communication is concerned, this should not pose problems: this type of communication is similar to that employed in Mediterranean countries and lays some emphasis on gestures. Moreover, there is no ban that will hinder the free circulation of advertising messages.

The advertising style most frequently employed in Argentina is the persuasive one, especially when cultural trends are at stake that may jeopardize the outcomes of advertising campaigns employing an informative style. In this respect, Argentines have a clear preference for visual and straightforward communicative practices. It is the persuasive style that attracts their attention more. Moreover, it has to be kept in mind that the level of fatalism is quite high.

The most powerful advertising medium in Argentina is television broadcasting. Argentines love watching television and have a passion for *telenovelas* and reality TV shows. IKEA's commercials vary according to the host country, even though they all share the image of the brand, one that values family and love, and is aware of current social trends. These commercials do not send boring messages and are always ironic and thought-provoking. They often feature unusual characters such as transvestites and divorced women, though the final suggestion by the brand is always that of "tidying up". Copywriters from local advertising agencies with an expertise in the field can be consulted as they should know how to incorporate their knowledge into the spirit that IKEA wants to express through its advertisements. It is fundamental that the product be presented as

reliable on account of the Argentines' high levels of risk-aversion, as already discussed in section two, and their constant need to be reassured.

Distribution Policy

The map of IKEA stores is such that while shopping customers have to follow a one-way path through the premises and therefore get the chance to see all the goods on display. In other terms, they cannot go directly to the area they need, as is the case in most shops. At the entrance they are given pencils and notebooks where they can take note of the products they would like to buy. Subsequently, they walk through a market hall where articles of small and medium size can be purchased. Eventually there is a wide self-service area where the notebooks may help customers find the items selected, that come in flat packages. At the end of the path, customers reach the counter. Many stores also have a restaurant with a fast food area where customers can eat, a hall with special offers and a shop selling food, most of which is Swedish.

Price Policy

Costs to be taken into consideration regard the production, sales, commercialization, foreign operations management (executives, partners, administration), promotion, stock management, packaging, labeling and transport. In this case export, custom duty and tax, barrier and intermediary costs have not to be faced.

As regards the competitive situation, it has already been observed that current prices are higher than those IKEA could be able to charge. Argentines are used to deal with disambiguated prices as well as with clear information as to the data that account for those prices. In general, they have a cost consciousness as well as a status consciousness and they are likely to be loyal to brands. As regards an estimation of elasticity, to the consumer the IKEA product has distinguishing traits; besides there are few replacement products being sold for the same or a higher price: overall unit costs are lower than those of the competing companies. And since IKEA is present in many markets, it can usually charge the same price, except for small variations occurring when the product was manufactured close to the place

where it is sold. This choice prevents the emergence of parallel markets and provides the customers with the possibility to find the same products at the same price in other markets. In this way, the demand tends to be aware of the existence of a “global price”.

As reported in the third section of this essay, IKEA prices are regarded as neither low nor too high, at least by young people of eighteen to thirty years of age. In other terms, IKEA products do not require too great an effort to be bought and they are either cheaper or as cheap as the equivalent products currently being sold in Argentina.

CONCLUSIONS

A goal of this essay has been to demonstrate that official data and economic parameters should always be considered in the light of the cultural and anthropological profiles of the countries where a company is either investing or meant to invest. Moreover, it has been shown that an insight into the segments being targeted foster further and most profitable opportunities to learn and exchange for any companies and for foreign companies in particular. Argentina is a big country where each region has some peculiarities. However, the cultural framework is rather homogeneous and what should not be forgotten is that when one refers to Argentina it is actually to the Buenos Aires area only that s/he is arguably referring to. This is certainly the most important region from an economic and demographic viewpoint, while the other regions show dissimilar characteristics.

To engage in discussions with young Argentines aged between eighteen and thirty years has paved the way for a better understanding of the context foreign companies could enter. In particular, it has provided us with useful data upon which the marketing mix management of the IKEA group – as it is presented here – has been based.

Foreign companies should not neglect the opportunity to gain deep insight into a country before investing there. A combination of economic information and the company's competitive advantage on the one hand, and of cultural knowledge on the other hand, is exactly what can ensure the success of a company entering a new market. Moreover, such combination can also ensure a long-term stay

during which the company may gain valuable experience to be put in practice again, in the new markets of the future.

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